

Connections between Incentive Behavior and User Engagement: Evidence from Stack Overflow

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ABSTRACT

To motivate user contributions, websites that feature user-generated content often implement incentive hierarchies. Badges are awarded to users for behaviors such as completing a certain number of actions of a specific type. Yet the existing empirical literature remains largely unclear whether and how badges can influence and steer user behavior. This paper examines the impact of badges on user activities in an online Q&A community, namely StackOverflow.com. By characterizing distinct patterns of change in user effort, we evaluate how users in different trajectory groups respond to badges. Our findings show that the group-based trajectory model can identify five distinct behavior patterns and badges play a significant role in specific groups. Furthermore, we find that the steering effect varies for badges of different classes and categories. From a dynamic perspective, we argue that incentivizing behavior does not work for everyone but can be an important predictor of user engagement behavior trajectories.

KEYWORDS

Online Q&A community; incentive mechanism; virtual badges; user behavior; active participation

INTRODUCTION

Community-based question-and-answer (Q&A) websites have become increasingly popular in recent years as an alternative to general-purpose Web search engines (Pnina et al., 2011). To improve user engagement, online knowledge exchange platforms typically set up various motivation measures (Anderson A et al., 2012). Previous studies have shown that badges can “steer” people's behavior towards substantially increasing the number of contributions before obtaining the badge, and immediately decreasing their contributions thereafter (Li Z et al., 2012). In contrast, evidence also suggests that one size does not fit all and the steering effect depends on the type of user (Yanovsky S et al., 2020; Hoernle Net al., 2020). Moreover, researchers also found that the positive effect on user contribution appears only temporary (Goes et al., 2016). Thus, there remains a significant gap in our understanding of how incentive behavior affects user engagement and how badges play its role in users' engagement behavior trajectories.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research Questions

Our research tries to explore how user behavior changes over time and the role incentives play in this process. Specifically, we focus on the following research questions:

- (1) How do user engagement behavior trajectories change over time?
- (2) How does the incentive mechanism affect the user participation behavior?
- (3) Does incentive mechanism have the same effect on different user groups?

From a simple Q&A site to a massive social community, Stack Overflow has evolved into a platform where knowledge seekers and providers of all levels of expertise interact with each other (Anderson A et al., 2013). It has established a trust evaluation system through “Reputation Point” and “Badge” to effectively motivate participants. Thus, for the last two questions, we chose badge awards as a representative of the incentive mechanism. The platform offers a variety of badge types and levels, which are mainly investigated from two dimensions: the quantity and quality of posts. To guarantee the internal validity of our findings, we mainly investigate the user participation behavior from the quantity dimension in this paper, thus the badges related to the quantity of user behavior are mainly considered. Three types of badges, gold, silver, and bronze, were selected for the badge level.

Data collection

For our analysis we collected data spanning four years from 2018 to 2021 from a programming-related Q&A site, Stack Overflow, which is publicly available on the site. To response our research question of how user behavior patterns change over time, we needed to ensure that each user had the same observation period, so we selected the users who registered between 01/06/2018 to 31/05/2019, which includes 302,078 users and 3,176,254 posts and observed their behavior changes for two years from the beginning of registration. We are particularly interested in three types of active participation behaviors: question, answer, and comment. As is shown in table 1, in our observational data, most users only post a few times. Users who are less active than half of the average daily activity ($1/2A$) are categorized as low active users; those who are more active than $1/2A$ but less than A are

categorized as active users; and those who are more active than A are categorized as high active users. As a result, we use the average daily activity of 1 as a division standard, which is the total activity of 672 over two years as a threshold A. The specific division results are displayed in Table 2. The behavior changes prior to and following badge acquisition were examined in a total of 622 users in the active group and the high-active group.

Number of posts	Number of users (proportion)
[1, 10]	244,659 (80.99%)
(10, 1000]	57,279 (18.96%)
(1000, 17123]	140 (0.05%)

Groups	Threshold value	Number of users (proportion)
Low-active users	[0, 336)	301,459 (99.79%)
Active users	[336, 672)	411 (0.14%)
High-active users	[672, 19591)	211 (0.07%)

Table 1. Distribution of number of posts by users

Table 2. Result of user division based on user activity

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Question 1: How does the incentive mechanism affect the participation behavior of users?

We used 617 users as research subjects, collected all the badge data they earned, used the time when users first earned badges as the origin, examined the user involvement patterns before and after that time point, and then averaged all user data to examine the motivating impact of badges on users. To cover most of the sample users, we set an observation window of 200 days before and after the badge acquisition, which may cover 90% of users. The results are displayed in Figure 1. Clearly, that engagement behavior starts to increase around 75 days before badge acquisition, and the closer to the badge goal, the more obvious this increase trend becomes. After earning the badge, user engagement gradually decreases and returns to the previous level.

Figure 1 Average number of posts per day, centered around the day zero for achieving the badge

Question 2: Does incentive mechanism have the same effect for different user populations?

In order to investigate the distribution and change patterns of user participation behavior over time, we used Group-Based Trajectory Modeling (GBTM) to classify user behavior trajectories. Based on the inherent heterogeneity among individuals, the number and shape of trajectory groups that characterize the change trend of data can be identified, so that individuals can be assigned to the most appropriate group. Each curve is a visual representation that can relatively accurately describe the individual development heterogeneity (NAGIN D. S. et al., 2010).

Each user receives 24 observation points for their monthly data on the number of posts made within two years after their registration. Based on GBTM, individuals in the same clusters following similar progressions in targeted behavior over time. In this study, the model can capture different users' participation behavior pattern over time using a variety of straight and curved trajectories. As is shown in Figure 2, the users' behavior trajectory is divided into five categories. The second group has the largest number of users at 60.7% and maintains a consistent low level of platform involvement. The third group has the second-highest number of users, which has a high level of participation in the early stage of registration and decreases over time, and previous studies have also shown that user participation levels continue to decline over time (Lu Y et al., 2017; Andruff H et al., 2013). Group 1 comprises 11.9% of the sample and shows modest participation at registration but increases steadily to a high level over time. In the remaining two groups, the level of participation of Group 4 users remained at a high level, but show an

overall decrease over time. Users in group 5 are the most active and their participation behavior has always remained at a high level without any short-term downward trend. Although Group 5 made up only 1.1% of the sample, its curve also shows typical user behavior which deserve studying.

Our main concern in this section is whether different user groups respond to badges differently as incentives. To investigate this, we used the user behavior trajectory grouping results from section 3.1, shown in Figure 3, which illustrates how various user groups' participation levels changed over the course of 120 days before and after receiving the badge. As can be seen from the figure, the first group of users are the most obvious target audience for badge incentives. Due to the guiding influence of badges, people in this category progressively start using the platform actively. Additionally, group 2 users, who are known for their low average activity and stable engagement, are also responsive to badges. As a result, even while badge awards have a positive directing effect, this effect is relatively weaker for them than for group 1. The remaining three user groups are less motivated by badges, with group 4 and group 5 users being extremely active and frequently authorities or experts in the community. These users' participation behavior is frequently motivated internally, and external incentive mechanisms like badges have little impact on them. Group 3 users initially demonstrated positive engagement, but their activity gradually decreased. Their behaviors were not obviously motivated by badges, and they gradually faded away from the platform due to the lack of motivation to participate in the knowledge activities.

Figure 2 The five-group user behavioral trajectory **Figure 3** Number of attempts for users of different groups

Question 3: The diminishing effect of badge incentives.

In this section, we explore whether the increase of participation levels varies for different users before they receive Bronze, Silver, and Gold. The badges are categorized into three levels and the corresponding user participation behavior curves are shown in Figure 4. From the point where the curve starts to rise, users who are about to receive gold badges show an earlier acceleration upward trend. From the perspective of the change of user participation level before and after obtaining the badge, users who obtained bronze badges and silver badges often gradually returned to their previous level after obtaining badges, but for users who obtained gold badges, although their curve declined relative to the time point of obtaining badges after obtaining badges, they remained at a high level. From the time point where the curve reaches its peak, the time point of obtaining the bronze badge is the closest to the peak point, while the other two badges have a certain time gap difference, which may be due to the fact that the silver and gold badge incorporate more quality indicators, so the user needs to wait for a period of time after actively posting to get the corresponding badge, and their post quality will be verified by the platform and other users.

Figure 5 shows the results from counting the involvement patterns of 497 users who had received gold badges in our sample during the 25 days before and after they received their gold, silver, or bronze badges. From the perspective of the occurrence time of the peak, similar to the results in Figure 4, there is a certain time difference between the time when the user obtains the silver badge and the gold badge and the peak point of the participation level. From the overall participation level, from high to low are silver badge, gold badge, bronze badge, and the difference is that the peak level of gold badge participation is lower than that of silver badge, which may be because the gold badge is not only depends on the number of posts, the quality factor also has a more complex influence mechanism on the acquisition of its badge, so compared with the bronze badge and silver badge, the gold badge has a relatively small impact on the number of user posts. From the perspective of participation behavior before reaching the peak (sub-graph in Figure 5), as the badge level increases, the curve rises more slowly. This means that although users will be motivated by the badge incentives to increase the frequency of participation before obtaining badges at all levels, the

higher-level target badges have less incentive effect. The influence of the badge shows a decreasing effect in the overall process of changing the user's badge goal from low to high.

Figure 4 Number of attempts for different levels of badges

Figure 5 Number of attempts for specific users before they receive Bronze, Silver, and Gold

CONCLUSIONS

This study proves that: The badge mechanism has an obvious incentive effect on users' participation behavior. With the accumulation of user experience, different badge levels have different incentive effects on user participation behavior, primarily showing a marginal decreasing effect. The higher the user level, the smaller the role of receiving badge incentives. Moreover, to some extent, different behavior patterns reveal user's preferences and characteristics for community activity participation. For users with different preferences, the badge mechanism also exhibits different incentive effects. Overall, the incentive mechanism serves as the user's primary source of motivation for users with low participation. To our knowledge, this study is the first to examine the group trajectory of user participation behavior across the period after entering the platform and to identify the connections between badge incentives mechanism and different user behavior trajectory.

Based on the findings above, more in-depth research needs to be conducted on online knowledge communities' incentive mechanisms and the factors affecting user behavior trajectories, including:

- (1) Expanding the research sample and expand the verification of the observed research conclusions;
- (2) Using mathematical model to quantitatively verify the impact of badge incentive mechanism on user behavior.
- (3) On the basis of sub-group of user behavior trajectory, we will further involve more factors affecting user behaviors in terms of platform incentive mechanism.

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